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Universidad
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Unibertsitatea

On Deep Learning for Computational Ethology

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1. Introduction

1.1 Computational Ethology

Behavior: The set of muscular responses of a living being because of an external stimulus and internal motivation.

Computational Ethology (CE):

- Discipline that studies the animal behavior
- Using the advances in Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence.
- Focused on the natural behavior to perform real-world tasks
- In unrestricted environments
- Quantitative behavior characterization.

Pharmacological point of view: CE is useful to test new medicines comparing the effect on different subjects, obtained by genetic modifications.

1. Introduction

1.2 State of the art in Computational Ethology

Sensors:

- RGB / depth / infrared cameras
- Pressure sensors
- Inertial sensors
- Microphones

Applications based on Artificial Intelligence:

- Tracking applications: DeepLabCut, Bonsai, SLEAP, ...
- Behavior classification: JAABA, DeepEthogram, VAME, ...
- Strain classification: SVM, k-NN

Bonsai

2. Research Question

Is it possible to implement a **strain classifier** from **pressure signal** and images by applying **pre-trained models** and **transfer learning**?

We focus on comparing spectrogram images from piezoelectric sensor during **locomotion periods**.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Animals and Experimentation

12 mice with 2 different strains:

- 7 wild-type (WT): non-mutated gene
- 5 transgenic Fmr1-knockout (Fmr1-KO): animal model to study Fragile X Syndrome

Recording system:

- Opaque-walled cage
- Base: piezoelectric platform with 3 sensors (20 kHz)
- Top video camera (25 fps)
- Computer with the Spike software to record piezoelectric signal

Animals introduced individually.

Procedure in accordance with EU directives for animal protection.

3. Materials and Methods

3.2 Behavioral Data Processing

<http://chronux.org/>

<https://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>

3. Materials and Methods

3.2 Behavioral Data Processing

Save centroid (x, y) in a .csv file

3. Materials and Methods

3.2 Behavioral Data Processing

<http://chronux.org/>

<https://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>

3. Materials and Methods

3.2 Behavioral Data Processing

Table 1. Parameters for spectrogram computation with Chronux library.

Parameters	Value 1	Value 2	Default values
Window size (s)	1	2	-
Windows step (s)	0.1	0.2	-
Tapers	[4, 2]	[3, 5]	[3, 5]: A numeric vector [TW K] where TW is the time-bandwidth product and K is the number of tapers, less than or equal to $2TW-1$
Frequency of interest (Hz)	[1.5 - 40]	[4 - 112]	[0 - $F_s/2$] (F_s : sampling frequency)

3. Materials and Methods

3.2 Behavioral Data Processing

Table 2. Parameter for spectrogram computation with Sonic Visualizer.

Parameter	Value	Range of values
Colour	Green	[Green, Sunset, ... , Wasp, Ice, ...]
Scale	dB	[Linear, Meter, dB ² , dB, Phase]
Window size	256	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512, ... , 16384, 32768]
Overlap	93.75%	[none, 25%, 50%, 75%, 87.5%, 93.75%]
Show	All bins	[All Bins, Peak Bins, Frequencies]
Scale	Linear	[Linear, Log]

3. Materials and Methods

3.3 Model Training and Evaluation

Binary classification problem to discriminate two phenotypes: WT (class 0) and Fmr1-KO (class 1)

Transfer learning to spectrogram images during locomotion with:

- Alexnet
- GoogLeNet
- ResNet50

Dataset divided into two parts:

- 80% train set
- 20% test set

5-fold cross-validation

Accuracy, Recall, Precision, F1 score.

Parameter	Value
Solver	Adam
Learning rate	0.0001
Mini batch size	52
L2 Regularization	0.0001
Folds for Cross-validation	5

Algorithm	Execution time	Layers	Total learnables
AlexNet	≈ 35min	25 (depth 8)	56 876 418
ResNet50	≈ 4h	177 (depth 50)	23 538 690
GoogLeNet	≈ 2h	144 (depth 22)	5 975 602

4. Results

4.1 Results for Spectrogram computed with Chronux library

1 second window size and 0.1 seconds window step

Tapers	3 - 5				4 - 2			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	98.40%	1.00	0.97	0.98	100.00%	1.00	1.00	1.00
GoogLeNet	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	99.47%	1.00	0.99	0.99
ResNet50	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99

2 seconds window size and 0.5 seconds window step

Tapers	3 - 5				4 - 2			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	98.93%	0.98	1.00	0.99	96.79%	0.93	1.00	0.97
GoogLeNet	97.86%	0.97	0.99	0.98	97.33%	0.97	0.98	0.97
ResNet50	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	97.86%	0.97	0.99	0.98

4. Results

4.2 Results for Spectrogram computed with Sonic Visualizer

Window size - overlap	256 - 93.75%			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	100.00%	1.00	1.00	1.00
GoogLeNet	96.26%	0.93	0.99	0.96
ResNet50	96.79%	0.95	0.98	0.97

5. Conclusion and Future Work

Introduction of Computational Ethology and its state of the art.

Research question: Is it possible to discriminate phenotypes with pressure signals and images using transfer learning?

Binary classification problem with 2 different animal models:

- Wild-type
- Fmr1-KO

Spectrogram images from the piezoelectric pressure signal during locomotion periods.

Yes, we can differentiate phenotypes with high accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score.

Future work: apply this approach to an experimental study about healthy ageing in elderly to detect gait anomalies with recordings from an electroencephalogram (EEG) and a walking platform.

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